

FROM MICROSTRUCTURE CHARACTERIZATION TO MULTI-SCALE MODELLING OF INJECTED CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PEEK

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Keywords: *Injected PEEK/Carbon, SEM, damage, multiscale modelling*

1 Introduction

Composite materials are of main interest in transport fields, especially in aeronautic manufacturing, due to their excellent specific properties [1-2]. Thermosetting resins are very used, mainly because of their easy processing but are difficult to recycle. PEEK (poly-ether-ether-ketone) is a thermoplastic matrix exhibiting similar mechanical properties to epoxy. PEEK is a semi-crystalline thermoplastic polymer, it has very good mechanical and chemical properties [3]. Moreover, its glass transition temperature of 143°C and melting temperature of 343°C allow it to be used at high temperature [2]. The classical AS4/APC2 prepreg, PEEK reinforced by continuous carbon fibre is used for simple and double curvature parts. Injection-moulding is a good process for complex shapes. A major difference resides in the shortness of the fibres. Thus, damage phenomena are modified compared to composite laminates.

Mechanical predictions are important to monitor effectiveness of a designed part. The microstructure has to be investigated in order to understand damage behaviour. Micromechanical modelling based on mean-field homogenization enables to care about distributions of orientation and length of fibres, and PEEK crystallization rate.

2 Material and processing – injection moulding of 90HMF40TM

In this study, a commercial grade of carbon-fibre-reinforced-PEEK is used: 90HMF40TM supplied by Victrex[®]. This material features 40-wt% of short carbon fibres and a 90G PEEK grade. Tests specimens, manufactured according to ISO 3167,

have been moulded with a DK 65/160 injection-moulding machine.

3 Material characterization at macro and micro scales

3.1 Mechanical characterization – monotonic and cyclic tensile tests

3.1.1 Testing machine and procedure

Monotonic and cyclic tensile tests were carried out on a tensile testing machine SCHENCK tensile test machine with hydraulic grips respecting NF ISO 527-2 norm, see Fig. 1. Two kinds of loading-unloading tests were performed, one operated by crosshead speed (5mm/min) and the other by force speed (30kN/min).

Fig. 1. Tensile testing machine with an infrared camera.

An infrared camera was set in front of the specimen to monitor its temperature with respect to mechanical state.

3.1.2 Monotonic tensile tests – characterization of macro mechanical properties

Monotonic tensile tests gave access to Young modulus, tensile strength and elongation at break, gathered in Table 1. Fig. 2 illustrates the behaviour of 90HMF40TM under quasi-static monotonic tensile loading.

Young modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
43.45 ± 1.15	317.12 ± 10.21	1.00 ± 0.07

Table 1. Mechanical properties of 90HMF40TM.

As it is shown, the behaviour of 90HMF40TM is non-linear with a linear part until 100MPa (neat PEEK tensile failure).

Fig. 2. Stress versus strain curve : monotonic tensile behaviour of 90HMF40TM.

3.1.3 Cyclic tensile tests – illustration of non-linear phenomena

The aim of these tests is to see the behaviour of the material while loading and unloading at different strain (or stress) levels. First we have to avoid the compressive state in order to stay in tension. Fig. 3 shows the behaviour of 90HMF40TM for a cyclic tensile test.

Fig. 3. Stress versus strain curve – cyclic tensile behaviour of 90HMF40TM.

Under a stress of 100MPa loads and unloads are on the same path, it means that neither plasticity nor damage occurred. Whereas, for higher levels of solicitations, plastic strain (non return to 0% of strain after an unloading at 0MPa) increases. If stress is plotted versus plastic strain (Fig. 4), the macro hardening law is defined.

Fig. 4. Stress versus plastic strain curve – macroscopic hardening of 90HMF40TM.

Defining a law of hardening (Eq. 1), and fitting with experimental data we found the results gathered in Table 2.

$$R(\varepsilon_p) = R_0 \cdot (1 - \alpha \cdot e^{-\beta \varepsilon_p}) \quad (1)$$

R ₀	α	β
250	2500	0.6

Table 2. Hardening law parameters of 90HMF40TM.

Moreover, for each cycle *i*, Young modulus is calculated (*E_i*). Thus it is possible to calculate the

macroscopic damage of each cycle i with (Eq. 2). Damage is plotted versus applied stress on (Fig. 5).

$$d_i = \frac{E_i}{E_0} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 5. Damage versus stress – macroscopic damage law of 90HMF40TM.

To have a better understanding, E_0 was taken as the maximum calculated Young modulus. We can notice that before 100MPa, damage is decreasing, meaning that cycling in the “elastic” part the material is being stiffer. There may be an influence of residual stress due to processing conditions (not taken into account in this study). Whereas, from 100MPa to failure, damage is slightly growing to a value of 4%.

3.2 Identification of non-linear phenomena

3.2.1 Scanning Electron Microscopy

In order to reveal damage phenomena after tensile tests, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) technique was used on fracture surfaces with a Nova NanoSEM 450 SEM. On Fig. 6, we can notice that only debonding (A zone) and plasticity (B zone) of the matrix affect the behaviour of the composite material. No fibre breakage was observed, fibre length being smaller than critical length. A cut of specimen section, perpendicular to the injection flow, enabled to measure the distribution of orientation of the fibres by image analysis.

Fig. 6. SEM photography of a fracture surface.

Hence, two non-linear have to be modelled : interface failure and PEEK plasticity.

3.2.2 Infrared thermography

An infrared monitoring was employed during tensile tests to improve the determination of damage and plasticity laws. On Fig. 7, stress and temperature variation are plotted versus test time.

Fig. 7. Stress and temperature versus time Identification of damage scenario.

Indeed, until a stress value of 100MPa, temperature is decreasing linearly, revealing the macro “elastic” behaviour of the material. From this value to 250MPa, the temperature is taking off from the previous slope. Plasticity and damage occurring, non-linear phenomena induce non-reversible thermodynamic effects, hence, an elevation of temperature. We can see that damage is not important because of loading and unloading slopes that are straight. After 250MPa, temperature slopes

are fluctuating, indicating that there is a debonding, so a sliding, between fibres and the matrix.

Thus, the non-linear behaviour is determined to be firstly plasticity and damage in a second time.

3.3 Identification of fibre length and orientation distributions

In a homogenization approach, it is of main interest to have access to fibre length and orientation distributions in order to model accurately the material mechanical behaviour.

3.3.1 Fibre length distribution

To measure fibre length distribution in the material, it has been necessary to extract fibres from the matrix by dissolution. Afterwards, we dispersed them on a glass blade and made multiple photographs, with a Keyence VHX-1000, like (Fig. 8) at a x200 magnification.

Fig. 8. Photograph of fibres at x200 magnification.

Thanks to a macro developed with Aphelion[®], it was possible to measure fibres by image analysis. Post-processing data with Matlab[®] enables to have the histogram of fibre length distribution (Fig. 9). A special focus was made on the number of fibres analysed, approximately 1000 per histogram.

Fig. 9. Histogram of fibre length distribution of 90HMF40TM.

3.3.2 Fibre orientation distribution

To measure fibre orientation distribution in the material, it has been necessary to take photographs at x1000 in a Nova NanoSEM 450 at 20kV (Fig. 10). To be representative, pictures were made on the width of a section of the specimen, perpendicular to flow direction. 40 photographs were taken to cover the all width of the section.

Fig. 10. Photograph of specimen section at x1000 magnification.

As well as to analyse fibres length, Aphelion[®] enables to measure ellipse axes and so to determine fibre orientation. An inner laboratory code was developed to process these data and give access to Advani tensor, representative of orientation state of fibres in the section of the material. The global

Advani tensor of orientation is represented in (Eq. 3).

$$a_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.71 & -0.02 & 0.02 \\ -0.02 & 0.22 & 0.00 \\ 0.002 & 0.00 & 0.06 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The diagonal value of the matrix are the most interesting. One can notice that the a_{33} component is very low (6%), meaning that there are few fibres in the Z-direction. Meanwhile, a_{11} (71%) is greater than a_{22} (22%).

4 Multi-scale modelling

4.1 Elastic homogenization

4.1.1 General Mori-Tanaka approximation

Homogenization scheme chosen is based on Mori-Tanaka [4] work, improved by Benveniste [5] in order to predict elastic properties of short fibre composite in the elastic domain. (Eq. 4) specifies the equation applied to get access to macro stiffness tensor from micro properties.

$$L_{MT} = L_m + \sum_{i=1}^N v_i \cdot (L_i - L_m) : A_i : \left[v_m \cdot I + \sum_{i=1}^N v_i \cdot A_i \right]^{-1} \quad (4)$$

With the localization tensor of Eshelby inclusion problem (Eq. 5):

$$A_i = \left[I + E_{i,m} : M_m : (L_i - L_m) \right]^{-1} \quad (5)$$

With L_m (respectively L_i) matrix (respectively phase i) stiffness tensor, v_m (respectively v_i) the volume fraction of matrix (phase i), I the identity tensor, $E_{i,m}$ Eshelby tensor depending of phase i shape (aspect ratio = length / diameter) and matrix stiffness, M_m matrix compliance tensor.

4.1.2 Fibre length modelling

To take fibre length distribution into account, a mean on Eshelby tensor is done (Eq. 6):

$$\bar{E}_{i,m} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} v_i \cdot E_{i,m} \quad (6)$$

Taking the number of fibre length family N_i equals to 20, corresponding to fibre length distribution histogram (3.3.1).

4.1.3 Fibre orientation modelling

Orientation state is modelled considering Advani tensor, using Advani-Tucker law of orientation [7] for Eshelby tensor of localization (Eq. 7):

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{A}_i = & B_1 \cdot a_{ijkl} + B_2 \cdot (a_{ij} \cdot \delta_{kl} + a_{kl} \cdot \delta_{ij}) \\ & + B_3 \cdot (a_{ik} \cdot \delta_{jl} + a_{il} \cdot \delta_{jk} + a_{jl} \cdot \delta_{ik} + a_{jk} \cdot \delta_{il}) \\ & + B_4 \cdot (\delta_{ij} \cdot \delta_{kl}) + B_5 \cdot (\delta_{ik} \cdot \delta_{jl} + \delta_{il} \cdot \delta_{jk}) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Considering a linear closure approximation to have the fourth order tensor of orientation from the experimental second order tensor of orientation (Eq. 8). This closure approximation is relevant for “planar” orientation distribution.

$$\begin{aligned} a_{ijkl} = & -\frac{1}{35} \cdot (\delta_{ij} \cdot \delta_{kl} + \delta_{ik} \cdot \delta_{jl} + \delta_{il} \cdot \delta_{jk}) \\ & + \frac{1}{7} \cdot (a_{ij} \cdot \delta_{kl} + a_{ik} \cdot \delta_{jl} + a_{il} \cdot \delta_{jk} + a_{kl} \cdot \delta_{ij} + a_{jl} \cdot \delta_{ik} + a_{jk} \cdot \delta_{il}) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Coefficients B_1 to B_5 (Eq. 9) of Advani-Tucker equation depend on the fourth order tensor to orientate (in this case A_i):

$$\begin{aligned} B_1 = & A_{11} + A_{22} - 2 \cdot A_{12} - 4 \cdot A_{66} \\ B_2 = & A_{12} - A_{23} \\ B_3 = & A_{66} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_{23} - A_{22}) \\ B_4 = & A_{23} \\ B_5 = & \frac{1}{2} \cdot (A_{22} - A_{23}) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

4.1.3 Validation of elastic prediction

Taking into account inputs, gathered in Table 3, a relative error of 3% was found between experiment and modelling.

	Notation	Value
<i>Fibre</i>	E_f	400GPa
	ν_f	0.27
	r_f	5 μ m
<i>Matrix</i>	E_m	3.8GPa
	ν_m	0.325

Table 3. Model inputs for Mori-Tanaka’s approximation.

4.2 Plastic behaviour modelling – macroscopic law of plasticity

In a first approach, plasticity was considered macroscopically. A consideration of micro-plasticity would have need to linearize matrix mechanical behaviour, for example with the secant method [7-8]. Based on the basic law of plasticity (Eq. 10) with von Mises equivalent stress (Eq. 11), plasticity was implemented by an implicit formulation.

$$f = \sigma_{eq} - R(\varepsilon_p) \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_{eq} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \cdot \left(\sigma - \frac{1}{3} \cdot Trace(\sigma) \right) : \left(\sigma - \frac{1}{3} \cdot Trace(\sigma) \right)} \quad (11)$$

The hardening law $R(\varepsilon_p)$ is the one determined by fitting experimental data.

4.3 Damage criteria – Fitoussi

As it was observed by SEM, sources of composite failure are debonding and matrix plasticity. To model the damage of the interface, between fibre and matrix, Fitoussi criteria (Eq. 12) was employed [6].

$$\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_c} \right)^2 + \gamma \cdot \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_c} \right)^2 = 1 \quad (12)$$

Where σ_c and τ_c are the failure normal and tangential stress respectively, and γ a parameter of coupling (Table 4).

σ_c	τ_c	γ
100MPa	70MPa	0.4

Table 4. Fitoussi criteria parameters of the model.

5 Model validity

5.1 Model design

To confirm the validity of the model, a user material (UMAT) was developed with the help of the industrial software ABAQUS[®]. The geometry of the specimen (Fig.) was taken from the injection software Autodesk[®] Simulation Moldflow.

Fig. 11. ABAQUS[®] model geometry.

5.2 Comparison experiment / model

To compare and validate the model, experimental and model stress versus strain curves were plotted (Fig. 12). A relative error of prediction of 5% is achieved at 300MPa.

Fig. 12. Experimental data and model prediction of stress versus strain.

6 Conclusion

Microstructure characterization by SEM, distribution of fibre orientation and fracture surface observation, of injected carbon fibre reinforced PEEK enabled to understand its sources of damage. As a matter of fact, only debonding and matrix plasticity are responsible of material failure and not fibre breakage. On top of that, infrared thermography monitoring refine their scenario and law. Thus, the model was developed to take into account the observed phenomena. It features the ‘classical’ Mori-Tanaka homogenization scheme, used for short fibre composite prediction, and an implementation of nonlinear micromechanical phenomena. In order to confirm the model accuracy on the prediction, we used an user material behaviour UMAT with

ABAQUS[®]. Comparison of modelling results to experimental data gave a correspondence of 5%.

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